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Piano

& KEYBOARD

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How's the Balance?

by Karl Paulnack

While music for “keyboard plus other” has existed for hundreds of years, not until fairly late in this century did the music world conclude that this repertoire benefits from a pianist of special training and experience. The university, now nearly a thousand years old, has deemed this special training worthy of an academic degree only for the past few decades. While it is remarkable that the art of collaborative pianism would have been barely recognizable as a separate discipline fifty years ago, it is even more striking that defined areas of specialization within that art have developed so quickly.

For example, it seems that those pianists who work with singers do so to the exclusion of all other collaborative genera. Pianists who specialize in instrumental duo sonatas and chamber music are avoided by singers. The old joke—“If a singer hears that you play for violinists, he will assume you don’t know how to breathe; if a violinist hears that you play for singers, she will assume you have no technique”—still makes the rounds. An art only recently recognized as unique now seems to be evolving into distinct species.

Let me first point out that specialists have contributed profoundly to the state of collaborative art, and we owe them a debt of gratitude. Duos like Dietrich Fischer-Dieskau/Gerald Moore and Gerard Souzay/Dalton Baldwin, to name but two

examples of many, expanded our understanding of German Lieder and French Mélodie, respectively, in no small part because of their concentration in those areas. One could argue that with a collaborative repertoire so vast, it would be impossible to satisfactorily investigate music on a very high level without “breaking up into teams.” I have no wish to denigrate specialists, or to suggest that to specialize is somehow a bad thing, and I certainly want to acknowledge that spe-

pianist intent on a solo career essentially excludes any serious immersion in the song literature? Is it merely a coincidence that older musicians who remember Rubinstein’s generation of pianists complain that “pianists today don’t know how to sing—it’s all about higher-faster-louder?” Could we argue that in playing orchestral reductions, the act of trying as hard as possible to sound like an orchestra forces pianists to wring colors from the instrument

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cialists are, in large part, responsible for advancing the art.

Yet while acknowledging the contribution of specialists, I also want to suggest that the evolution of collaborative pianism into an art with increasingly obligatory specialization does not come without costs. Some of these are obvious. For example, is it really desirable that the intense training received by the

that we might not otherwise know were there, and that these colors are of great utility in the solo literature? Most collaborative pianists would agree that solo pianists lose something when they evade our literature. The question we avoid asking is what we lose as we get further and further away from theirs.

For me, the trickiest questions involve our specialized work with singers. I do

not have answers to all of these questions. I'm not sure I even know how to ask them politely, but I must ask them. They taunt me. Some questions are stated intentionally from the devil's advocate perspective; some are straightforward. I hope that discussion provoked by these questions will help illuminate what we do and why we do it.

Let me confess my biases up front. I love the vocal literature. The most exhilarating, intimate, and memorable experiences of my life as a collaborative pianist have happened with singers. The most frustrating experiences of my life have also happened with singers. While I devote a good part of my energies to the theory and practice of vocal accompaniment, I also perform—to the greatest extent possible—solo literature, concerti, string chamber music, and instrumental duo sonatas. I assist conductors as a rehearsal pianist. I teach not only vocal and instrumental accompanying, but give private lessons to undergraduate piano majors. My self-identity as a musician resides more squarely in the label “pianist” than it does in “accompanist” or “collaborator.” (The term “coach” still summons visions of myself in a baseball cap with a whistle around my neck shouting “sing, sing.”)

Tell a violinist how to play a sonata and you get a cold stare. Tell a singer how to sing an aria and you get a check. Pianists learn the social customs appropriate to their niche. We treat violinists like sovereign nations, but singers like little lambs. Am I the only one around who finds this odd?

Out of the specialization of playing with singers has evolved the pianist/coach. The necessity of the pianist/coach as “external ears” cannot be denied; the fact that the singer has a furious buzzing just inches away from the ears does make an informed, external hearer necessary. Like the singer, violinists often need to be told that they are playing out of tune, that the tone does not carry, or that the articulation is not

clear. Whereas violinists usually hire violinists as listeners, singers hire pianists called vocal coaches. To my knowledge, there are not a lot of pianists working as violin coaches. While we have many pianists who make their living telling singers which arias are just right for them, which notes they ought to interpolate on the da capo, or how to pronounce German vowels, it would be extremely rare for a pianist with even the most

extensive experience in string collaboration to suggest a fingering or a bowing, or to counsel the violinist on ornamentation or musical style. Such suggestions would most likely be regarded as inappropriate, condescending, or intrusive, because we assume that the training of the violinist readily equips her to address these issues. Tell a violinist how to play a sonata and you get a cold stare. Tell a singer how to sing an aria and you get a check. Pianists learn the social customs appropriate to their niche. We treat violinists like sovereign nations, but singers like little lambs. Am I the only one around who finds this odd?

Pianists who work professionally with singers are more or less presumed to be linguistic technicians, repositories of baroque ornamentation technique, consultants on musical style, historians of the performance traditions of operatic arias, and—sometimes—voice teachers. I have heard the arguments: singers start late due to the maturation of the voice; singers have an instrument that cannot be seen and must be intuited; and, with text and all, singers just can't learn all the things they need to know. This leads to my first set of questions.

To what extent, and for what specific purposes, are coaches necessary? To what

extent has the role of coach expanded beyond reasonable boundaries (the external, helpful set of ears) and taken over that which should rightly be the purview of singers and teachers of voice? What aspect of languages makes it reasonable to expect pianists, but not singers, to learn them? Do we unwittingly invite vocal students not to take seriously their pronunciation of French with the assumption that some future “coach” will “fix” it for the audition? What is it about baroque ornamentation that renders it the natural domain of pianists, but an area that eludes singers? The tradition of vocal ornamentation preceded that of the keyboard by several hundred years. How did we end up as the *encyclopedia ornamentatica*? Where were all the voice teachers? Wasn't anyone taking notes? To what extent is the coaching relationship a healthy, helper relationship, such as a doctor/patient or teacher/student relationship? Do singers really need us to do all these things for them—or do we need to be needed? Are vocal coaches, as one of my more instrumentally oriented colleagues once whispered, “babysitters?”

Early in this century, collaborative pianists were seen as “factory seconds,” not “real” pianists, but well-suited to the task of assistant. It is rumored that accompanists on tour with soloists were often expected to carry the baggage of the soloist and attend him as a personal assistant, all for a fee that was a small percentage of the artist's management fee. We did not agree to this arrangement because it was in the best interest of the art, nor because it inspired us to excel. We did so because of market conditions. The economics of the job determine, to a larger extent than we might like to admit, the practice of the art.

To what extent do current economics affect the quality of our art? What does the diminishing market for art song recitals portend in terms of the practice of our art? Are we reversing roles—going from performing practitioners of the piano who are occasionally helpful to singers due to our knowledge of the voice, becoming instead practitioners of voice and language who occasionally play the piano? If, in fact, we are becoming linguists, aria gurus, and de facto teachers of singing in order to compensate for the fact that our performing venues are drying up, is this the right response?

Would our energies be better spent developing appreciation, audiences, and venues for the performance of the art? Is the “special skills” package that is becoming increasingly assumed of pianists who work with singers getting out of hand? No one would debate that a thorough command of languages is essential to an informed performance of the vocal literature. But remember our history. We all too easily accommodate the demands of the market. Are we again carrying baggage (at our own expense) that does not belong to us? Is this growing range of adjuvant skills a defensive reaction to the continuing notion that we are somehow a second class of pianist? Do we truncate our own existence as pianists by forever leaving the solo literature in order to take care of our clients’ needs? Will it someday be more important to know the spelling for the irregular verbs in *subjunctif imparfait* than to play with an absolutely gorgeous sound? Fifty years from now, will we look back and wonder why we are still not taken seriously as pianists?

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ought to ask the same questions as a person
who has had psychotherapy for 20 years.
Am I able or willing to do this for myself now?
Am I getting any better?*

Some of these questions have answers; some, like the Zen *koan*, illuminate balance simply through repetition. I believe in vocal coaches and not in violin coaches if only because most violinists get their first instrument at around seven years of age, whereas when most singers get theirs, they are closer to 27. Hindered by an anatomical late start, singers are then bequeathed an enormous number of languages to learn, roles to assimilate, and a repertoire that spans most of notated music history. Having a helper for a period of time seems entirely reasonable. But a helper should be a helper and not a way of life; one eventually walks unassisted. My colleague, Margo Garrett, once wisely remarked that while she loves coaching and devotes herself to the singer in the

coaching studio, a clear goal in her mind is to “get the singer out of my studio and on his own as quickly as possible.” A vocal coach must have a specific and finite vision of his or her role in working with the singer—a vision actively supported by singers and voice teachers. A singer who has had vocal coaching for 20 years ought to ask the same questions as a person who has had psychotherapy for 20 years. Am I able or willing to do this for myself now? Am I getting any better? Perhaps if we acknowledge that it is just a little weird to have all of these pianists running around telling all of these singers what to do, the boundaries of what we do will be established with greater care.

The role of external set-of-ears makes complete sense to me. I have no trouble with the idea of providing some help with languages and some guidance on style. I don’t even mind (occasionally) hearing a pianist plunking out notes for a young singer with a late musical start as long as that kind of thing is temporary.

Why pianists, and not singers, seem to be entrusted with the handing down of vocal performance practice—what to do with a da capo, who takes time where in which arias, which role is right for which voice—is a mystery to me.

While there is a place for vocal coaches, I must go back to my original concern with overspecialization. It will be a sad day when performances of Rachmaninoff songs are played only by pianists who understand the rules for Russian consonant palatization. I hope we never reach the point where singers shun pianists who could care less how a diphthong is produced, but who would love to give their all in a *Dichterliebe* or two. It would be a shame if pianists who feel attracted to the song literature were

frightened off by the increasingly long list of things that singers want and need from a pianist. What about that which pianists need from singers? It is marvelous that we have developed a whole new breed of pianist genetically predisposed to provide singers with everything they’ve ever dreamed of in a set of ears and a pair of hands. The danger is that pianists who don’t speak seven languages, or know a hundred roles, will mistakenly believe that they are not supposed to play songs.

Every serious musician needs to know the voice and the vocal repertoire. All music descends from and, if properly performed, returns to the model of the voice. The highest compliment for any instrumentalist is to hear that the playing sings. Every piano teacher I know has, at one time or another, urged a student to “sing, sing!” There is a role for helpers and for specialists; but the song literature is too important to all musicians for it to be increasingly sequestered among a small group of experts. It is curious that the meteoric rise in the number and quality of specialized vocal pianist-coaches has been accompanied by plummeting interest in, and market for, the song recital. I won’t infer a necessarily causal relationship, but I worry about the implication that song literature is the domain of specialists.

I suppose that in my vision of the perfect world, pianists would play a concerto one week, a song recital the next, and music for string trio the week after that. (In my vision of the perfect world, each of us would also be independently wealthy and have enormous amounts of practice time.) Pianists who play by themselves would not forget how to sing and to breathe. Those who play only lieder would not forget how to rise up and command the spotlight when the music demands it. Those in front of orchestras too generous in sound would remember what we learned from singing—that when it comes to tone, we never, ever, force. The song literature must not be declared off-limits to the generalist pianist. The solo literature must not be abandoned by collaborators en masse. We need each other. The presence of specialists adds to our corporate knowledge. It should not encourage the elimination of individual breadth. ❖